

FILM FUSION SYSTEM

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Abstract. Film Fusion System is an advanced movie database website for movie enthusiasts. Customers can register and log in to save favorite movies, rate films, and leave comments. The system is built using Java Spring Boot, Thymeleaf, MySQL, and Bootstrap, offering a user-friendly design. It includes features like dynamic notifications, a theme toggle for dark and light modes, and a responsive layout. Film Fusion provides a comprehensive and enjoyable movie exploration experience.

Keywords: film fusion, relational database, web development

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, the importance of a robust Movie Management System (MMS) is paramount. Movie enthusiasts and administrators need a reliable platform to manage vast amounts of movie data, ensuring easy accessibility and efficient resource management. Film Fusion System offers a centralized platform accessible over the internet, enabling users to explore movie collections and administrators to manage movie data seamlessly. The primary objective of this system is to transition from manually managed movie databases to automated, efficient, and user-friendly digital systems. This system caters to users who may not have the time to browse movie collections physically, offering a wide range of movies, trailers, ratings, and user reviews at their fingertips.

PROBLEM

The project "Film Fusion System" is developed using Java Spring Boot with Thymeleaf templates, focusing on core operations such as adding new movies, updating movie information, searching for movies, and managing user reviews and ratings. This project provides comprehensive information about movies, actors, trailers, and user ratings. Administrators can enter new movie records, retrieve details of existing movies, and manage user interactions. Customers can rate movies, leave comments, and save their favorite movies for later viewing. The system tracks the popularity of movies based on user ratings and reviews, providing valuable insights into user preferences.

APPROACH

Film Fusion System is designed to be the backbone of any movie database, recognizing the importance of well-organized movie information for both entertainment and educational purposes. It provides detailed information about movies, users, and their interactions. The system monitors the availability of movies and tracks user activity, showcasing popular movies among users. It can generate management information system (MIS) reports for administrative purposes, making it customizable for any specific requirements. The system also maintains records of user interactions, ensuring that late returns or penalties for overdue reviews are properly managed. Throughout the project, the focus has been on presenting information and user interactions in an intuitive and user-friendly manner.

In this system, customers must log in first. After logging in, customer must use payment system and then customers can search for movies they want to watch, view trailers, and read reviews. Additionally, users can rate movies, leave comments, and save movies to their profiles. Customers can also extend their review deadlines and provide feedback on the system. The system flow diagram shown in Figure 1 provides a visual representation of these processes.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes [2]. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. In the database, there are six data tables for the system. The tables are user, movie, save, comment, payment and notification. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

After the system is developed, system testing must be carried out to ensure it is free of bugs. If any bugs or errors are detected during testing, the developer must correct and fix them immediately. Testing evaluates the software to detect differences between given input and expected output. It is conducted to assess the system's quality and can be considered a validation and verification process. System testing is not limited to the development team but also involves specific outsiders to test system acceptance. Figure 3 shows the implementation of the Film Fusion System.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

The Internet has become a central resource in modern life, making a sophisticated movie database system like Film Fusion indispensable for both administrators and customers. Film Fusion offers efficient management of movie data, providing a comprehensive and engaging experience for customers who can explore extensive movie collections, save favorites, and leave reviews. Designed with intuitive navigation and a visually appealing interface, Film Fusion ensures quick data retrieval and valuable feedback. The system reduces manual workload, minimizes errors, and lowers operational costs, while enhancing user satisfaction and convenience through dynamic notifications, theme toggles, and responsive design. Integrated payment options allow for premium feature upgrades, further enriching the user experience. Overall, Film Fusion stands out as a leading solution for streamlining movie data management and offering a user-centric platform for movie enthusiasts.

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